

(Table 1 contd.)

Wheat ^b	1	10	9.10	91.0
	2	20	17.93	89.6
	3	40	36.20	90.5
Rice ^b	1	10	8.95	89.5
	2	20	18.32	91.6
	3	40	35.88	89.7
Beans ^b	1	10	8.97	89.7
	2	20	18.12	90.6
	3	40	36.56	91.4

*Mean of three replicate analyses.

^aAmount of sample = 50 ml

^b10 g of each sample was thoroughly washed prior to analysis and then BHC added.

The proposed method is sensitive, selective and superior to the Hancock's method as in the latter the dye formed is stable for only 5 min as compared to 30 h in the present method.

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Ir and Thermal Studies of Absorption Behaviour of Carbon Dioxide, Hydrogen Sulphide and Ammonia on Partially Silver(I)- and Nickel(II)-exchanged 5A Zeolites

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THE present study is devoted to using Ag^I and Ni^{II} ions for cation exchange with synthetic zeolite 5A and the new exchanged forms for interaction with carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulphide and

ammonia, to prepare adsorbed derivatives. These adsorbed derivatives have been investigated by ir spectroscopic and thermal methods. Physical or chemical adsorption of gases is clearly indicated by ir adsorption bands. Discrete steps for the desorption of adsorbed and coordinated species as well as oxidation of reacted molecules have been reported together with weight loss data.

Commercial 5A zeolite, Ca₆Al₁₂Si₁₂O₄₈·30H₂O^I (Union Carbide) in powdered form was repeatedly treated with a saturated aqueous silver(I) nitrate and nickel(II) nitrate (both AnalaR). The resulting partially exchanged Ag^I and Ni^{II}-zeolite were filtered, washed free of excess ions and dried in air. A portion of these samples was interacted with gaseous carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulphide and ammonia in oxygen and moisture free environment. The ir spectra were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out in air at heating rate of 15° min⁻¹ upto 1000° on a Stanton Redcroft STA 780 automatic derivatograph.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra of carbon dioxide adsorbed Ag^I-exchanged 5A zeolite reveal only a weak band at about 2 310 cm⁻¹ due to the ν₃ vibration of physically adsorbed carbon dioxide. In the case of hydrogen sulphide adsorbed black derivative of Ag^I-5A zeolite, the bands become more intense especially at 460, 3 410 and 1 640 cm⁻¹ suggesting the formation of silver sulphide and water molecules respectively due to the oxidation of hydrogen sulphide^{2,3}. There is also a broad and weak band at 1 200–955 cm⁻¹ suggesting the inclusion of adsorbed species within the zeolite framework⁴. Ammonia adsorption on Ag^I-exchanged zeolite produces the characteristically strong bands at 1 400 cm⁻¹ (H-N-H vibration), 3 400 (NH stretch) and 1 635 cm⁻¹ (NH bending) besides ν_{OH} and δ_{OH} vibrations. The ir spectra of carbon dioxide adsorbed Ni^{II}-zeolite exhibit band at 1 410 cm⁻¹ which represents carbonate formation. Adsorption of hydrogen sulphide produces bands around 1 410 (HS) and 450 cm⁻¹ (Ni-S). Adsorption of ammonia increases the intensity of hydroxyl stretching band at around 3 500 cm⁻¹. The band at 1 400 cm⁻¹ (H-N-H) is quite distinct.

TG analysis (Table 1) of carbon dioxide adsorbed Ag^I-zeolite derivative shows that after dehydration proceeding upto 190°, further weight-loss occurs upto 480° due to desorption of carbon dioxide. Weight-loss after 860° suggests decomposition. The hydrogen sulphide adsorbed Ag^I-zeolite loses weight in three steps. After dehydration and dehydroxylation proceeding upto 340°, there is a sharp weight-loss upto about 780° due to oxidation and decomposition of the adsorbed species. Ammonia adsorbed sample gives weight-loss of about 15%. There are also distinct steps for dehydration, desorption and decomposition of the adsorbed species. TG plot of

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF TG ANALYSIS

Zeolite	Total weight loss (%)	Weight loss (%) at different temp. (°C)
Ag ^I -5A + CO ₂	14.35	9.8 upto 190 3.7 upto 480 0.85 upto 860
Ag ^I -5A + H ₂ S	19.00	13.7 upto 175 3.9 upto 340 1.4 upto 780
Ag ^I -5A + NH ₃	15.00	10.5 upto 240 2.0 upto 355 2.5 upto 780
Ni ^{III} -5A + CO ₂	25.00	18.7 upto 258 5.6 upto 500 0.75 upto 960
Ni ^{II} -5A + H ₂ S	34.00	17.7 upto 220 16.4 upto 810 18.8 upto 150
Ni ^{II} -5A + NH ₃	26.00	2.8 upto 365 4.5 upto 690

carbon dioxide adsorbed Ni^{II}-zeolite is indicative of dehydration and desorption taking place. After dehydration proceeding upto 258°, desorption of carbon dioxide begins and this step is over by 500°.

The hydrogen sulphide adsorbed derivative exhibits a dehydration step at 220° followed by the oxidation and decomposition of adsorbed species. The ammonia adsorbed derivative loses weight in three steps. The derivative starts to lose weight around 150°. After dehydration and deammoniation upto 690° there is a fast weight-loss step suggesting further desorption of the coordinated and adsorbed species.

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